

Formulation And Evaluation of Anti-Tuberculosis Tablet by Using Mango Ginger

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ABSTRACT

The increasing resistance of mycobacterium tuberculosis to conventional anti-tubercular therapy has driven interest in plant-based alternatives. This study focuses on the formulation and evaluation of an anti-tubercular tablet using curcuma amada roxb. (mango ginger), a rhizome rich in labdane diterpene dialdehyde an active compound reported for its anti-mycobacterium properties. Compatibility between the mango ginger extract and selected pharmaceutical excipients was confirmed using Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy. Tablets were prepared via direct compression and evaluated through pre-compression (flow properties) and post-compression (hardness, friability, disintegration, weight variation, and dissolution) parameters. Among the five formulations (B1-B5), batch b3 emerged as the most promising, exhibiting acceptable mechanical strength, rapid disintegration, low friability, and the highest in vitro drug release (99% within 60 minutes). These findings support the potential of mango ginger in herbal anti-TB therapy, warranting further pharmacological and clinical validation.

Keywords: Mango ginger, Curcuma amada, Anti-tubercular tablet, Labdane Diterpene Dialdehyde, Herbal formulation.

INTRODUCTION

One of the oldest known human diseases and a leading cause of death globally is tuberculosis (TB), which is brought on by bacteria belonging to the mycobacterium tuberculosis complex. tuberculosis is the second leading cause of death worldwide, after HIV/AIDS and it remains a serious threat to human health[1]. Tuberculosis is an airborne bacterial infection caused by m. Tuberculosis which affects any part of the body and most commonly the lungs. M. Tuberculosis is exposed to the air as droplet nuclei from coughing, sneezing, shouting or singing of individuals with pulmonary or laryngeal TB. The droplet nuclei are inhaled and transmission occurs. It passes into the mouth or nasal cavity, upper respiratory tract bronchi and finally reaches into the alveoli in the lungs[2] The formulated tablet by using mango ginger which is used to treat tuberculosis. The chloroform extract of mango ginger rhizomes was used for the determination of anti-tubercular activity.

Labdane diterpene dialdehyde was exhibited strong anti-tubercular activity against mycobacterium tuberculosis[3]. Tablets are solid preparations that are nearly always meant to be used orally. They are made by compressing consistent quantities of particles and contain a single dose of one or more active components. The most often recommended dose form is tablets because they are a convenient way to administer drugs, offer consistent dosages across tablets, are stable under a variety of long-term storage settings, and can be made using high-speed compression, labelling, and packing equipment. Because of this, tablet manufacturing technology is continuously evolving to improve its capacity to precisely administer a desired medicine in a dose form meant for either rapid or prolonged therapeutic effects[4].

Advantages Of Tablet Dosage Form[5]:

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- 1) They are unit dosage forms and offer the greatest capabilities of all oral dosage forms for the greatest dose precision and the least content variability.
- 2) Ease of accurate dose.
- 3) Release rate of the drug from tablets can be tailored to meet pharmacological requirements.
- 4) Easiest and cheapest to package and strip.
- 5) Easy to swallow with least tendency for hang-up.
- 6) Sustained release product is possible by enteric coating.
- 7) Objectionable odour and bitter taste can be masked by coating technique.
- 8) greatest chemical and microbial stability over all oral dosage forms.
- 9) Product identification is easy and rapid requiring no additional steps when employing an embossed and/or monogrammed punch face.

Disadvantages Of Tablet Dosage Form[5]:

- 1) Difficult to swallow in case of children and unconscious patients.
- 2) Some drugs resist compression into dense compacts, owing to their amorphous nature, low density character.
- 3) Drugs with poor wetting, slow dissolution properties, optimum absorption high in GIT may be difficult to formulate or manufacture as a tablet that will still provide adequate or full drug bioavailability.
- 4) Bitter tasting drugs, drugs with an objectionable odour or drugs that are sensitive to oxygen may require encapsulation or coating. In such cases, a capsule may offer the best and lowest cost.

- 5) Administration of drug with low density characters and amorphous

Features Of Tablet[6]:

- 1) The Product Should Be Stylish, Unique, And Free Of Flaws Including Contamination, Chips, Cracks, And Discolouration.
- 2) It Must Be Strong Enough To Endure The Shocks That Are Experienced During Manufacturing, Packaging, Shipping, And Dispensing.
- 3) It Must Possess The Physical Stability To Hold Its Physical Characteristics Over Time.
- 4) It Must Have The Ability To Release The Medication's Agent (S) In The Body In A Consistent And Repeatable Way.
- 5) In Order To Prevent The Medicinal Agent(S) From Being Altered, It Must Possess Appropriate Chemical Stability Over Time.

Weighting, Milling, Granulation, Drying, Blending, Lubrication, Compression, And Coating Are Among The Unit Processes Needed To Manufacture Tablets.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

The formulation of the anti-tuberculosis tablet utilized several pharmaceutical Excipients alongside the active herbal ingredient, mango ginger (*curcuma amada*), which was procured from the local market and selected for its reported anti-tuberculosis activity. Starch, sourced from Chemdyes Corporation, was employed as a diluent to provide bulk and improve the compressibility of the tablet. Polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVPK-30), also obtained from Chemdyes Corporation, served as a binder to ensure cohesion among the powder particles. Croscopolvidone, purchased from Alpha Chemika, was incorporated as a Superdisintegrant to promote rapid tablet disintegration upon administration. Talc, acquired from Loba Chemie Pvt. Ltd., was included as a glidant to enhance powder flow during tablet compression. Lastly, magnesium stearate, obtained from Sisco Research Laboratories Pvt. Ltd., was used as

a lubricant to reduce friction between the tablet material and the machinery during production.

Apparatus

In the present study, a variety of analytical and pharmaceutical instruments were utilized to ensure precise formulation and evaluation of dosage forms. An analytical weighing balance (Wensar electronic balance) was employed to accurately measure the weight of materials used during the formulation process. Uv-visible spectroscopy (alpha-Chemica) was used to determine the concentration of unknown substances, playing a key role in the analytical estimation of drug content. A hot air oven (Adesh an ISO 9001:2001 certified company) was used for drying materials under controlled temperature conditions. The dissolution apparatus (Swastika scientific instruments) served to evaluate the drug release rate and bioavailability, which are critical parameters in assessing the in vitro performance of dosage forms. A tablet punching machine (Swastika scientific instruments, Ambalacant) was used for compressing the powdered formulations into tablets, ensuring uniform size and shape. The Monsanto hardness tester (Swastika scientific instruments) was utilized to assess the mechanical strength and hardness of the tablets. Lastly, a disintegration apparatus (Swastika scientific instruments) was employed to evaluate how rapidly the tablets disintegrate into smaller particles, an essential factor influencing drug absorption and therapeutic effectiveness. A Vernier calliper (Swastika scientific instruments) was utilized to measure the thickness of the tablets with high precision, ensuring uniformity across batches. The friability test apparatus (Swastika scientific instruments) was employed to assess the ability of tablets to withstand mechanical stress during handling, distribution, and manufacturing. This test is crucial in determining the durability of tablets in real-world conditions. Furthermore, a bulk density apparatus (Adarsh instrument) was used to determine the bulk and tapped densities of powders, which are important parameters influencing the flow properties and compaction behaviour during tablet formulation. These instruments collectively ensured that the developed dosage forms met the required quality standards.

Methods

Procedure for extraction[7]

Maceration is a traditional and widely used extraction method for isolating bioactive constituents from plant materials. In this study, the maceration technique was employed to extract non-polar Phytochemicals from mango ginger (*Curcuma amada*) powder, using chloroform as the extraction solvent.

Preparation of plant material:

Fresh rhizomes of mango ginger were collected, thoroughly washed with distilled water to remove soil and other impurities, and then shade-dried to preserve thermolabile compounds. Once dried, the rhizomes were ground using a mechanical grinder into a coarse powder and stored in an airtight container until extraction.

Maceration process:

A quantity of 10 grams of mango ginger powder was accurately weighed and transferred into a clean, dry glass container. To initiate extraction, chloroform was poured into the container, ensuring that the mango ginger powder was completely covered by the solvent.

The container was tightly closed to prevent evaporation and kept at room temperature (approximately 25–30°C) for a minimum period of three days (72 hours). During this time, the mixture was stirred manually two to three times daily to enhance solvent penetration into the plant cells and promote effective dissolution of bioactive constituents.

Separation of extract:

After the maceration period, the mixture was subjected to filtration using muslin cloth followed by Whatman no. 1 filter paper to separate the liquid extract from the solid plant residue.

Evaporation of solvent:

The filtrate, which contained the chloroform-soluble Phytochemicals was then allowed to evaporate at room temperature in a well-ventilated area.

Alternatively, evaporation can be carried out using a water bath at a controlled low temperature to avoid degradation of Thermolabile compounds. This step was continued until complete removal of chloroform, leaving behind a thick, semi-solid crude extract of mango ginger.

Storage of extract:

The obtained extract was carefully collected and stored in an amber-colored, airtight glass container.

Phytochemical test of mango ginger[8]:

Chloroform extract of mango ginger was subjected to qualitative analysis of various active constituents, such as Terpinoides [labdane diterpene dialdehyde, alkaloids, saponins, glycosides, tannins, phenol, flavonoids, cardiac glycosides.

Determination of calibration curve[9]:

Spectroscopy study of the mango ginger

Preparation of standard stock solution: accurately weigh 1000mg of mango ginger and will dissolve an minimum quantity of distilled water in 100ml volumetric flask and made up to 100 ml with distilled water to get the concentration of 1mg/ ml.(stock).

Determination of maximum wavelength (max): the UV spectrophotometer with 10mm quartz cuvettes use for determination of maximum wavelength. UV spectrum of mango ginger standard solution will record in the wavelength range of 200-800nm to determine detector wavelength of maximum absorbance (max) using distilled water as blank respectively and the graph will plot.

Preparation of calibration curve : this stock solution will further dilute to get a concentration of 100µg/ml (stockii). Stock ii solution will further dilute to get a series of 2ppm to 20ppm concentration. The absorbance of this solution will measure in a Uv spectrophotometer by taking distilled water as blank. The graph plot concentration vs. absorbance to obtain the standard calibration curve. Take stock iii as 0.2 ,0.4,0.6,0.8,1,1.2,1.4,1.6,1.8,2ml and make it 10ml by adding distilled water.

Compatibility study (FTIR)[10]

Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy was performed to identify mango ginger and analyse possible interactions between the drug and excipients. The FTIR spectra of the pure drug and formulated mango ginger tablet were recorded using the ftr-1700 shimadzu analyser. The spectra were obtained using the KBR pellet method, and characteristic peaks were analysed to confirm the presence of functional groups and ensure compatibility between the drug and Excipientes.

Melting point determination[11]

The melting point of the drug was determined by melting point determination apparatus. The drug was filled in a capillary tube and the melting point was measured with the help of a thermometer.

Preparation of tablet[12]

Method used: *wet granulation method*

Wet granulation was employed for the preparation of tablets containing the active pharmaceutical ingredient (API) *mango ginger*. This method enhances the compressibility and uniformity of the powder blend, ensuring consistent tablet quality.

Steps involved in the preparation process

1. Weighing and mixing of ingredients:

All ingredients, including the API (*mango ginger*) and excipients such as starch, pvp k30 (binder) HPMC(binder), Crosspovidone (super-disintegrant),and other necessary excipients, were accurately weighed using a calibrated digital balance. The ingredients were initially blended to achieve a homogenous dry mixture.

2. Preparation of the binder solution:

A binder solution was prepared using either:

Polyvinylpyrrolidone k30 (pvp k30) – used in three batches

Hydroxy propyl methylcellulose (HPMC) – used in two batches

The required quantity of binder (either PVP k30 or HPMC) was dissolved in purified water to obtain a viscous solution. This solution acted as the granulating fluid and starch paste is used as diluent.

3. Wet massing:

The binder solution and diluent (starch paste) were slowly added to the dry mixture of API and excipients while mixing continuously to form a wet mass. This process was performed manually in a clean, dry mixing mortar.

4. Granulation:

The wet mass was then passed through a 12# sieve to convert it into uniform-sized granules. This step ensures better flowability and compressibility during the compression stage.

5. Drying of granules:

The moist granules were dried in a hot air oven at 60°C until the desired moisture content was achieved. Proper drying is crucial to prevent microbial growth and maintain the stability of the formulation.

6. Sizing (milling):

The dried granules were passed through an 18# sieve to break down any oversized lumps. Further classification was done using 22# and 44# sieves:

Material retained on 22# sieve was collected as the final granules.

Material passed through 44# sieve was collected as fines.

The weight of both final granules and fines was recorded for each batch to ensure consistency and evaluate granulation efficiency.

7. Blending:

The final dried granules were blended with additional excipients to enhance the tablet properties. These included:

Lubricants (e.g., magnesium stearate) – to prevent sticking and reduce friction during compression.

Glidants (e.g., talc) – to improve the flow properties of the granules.

The blending was carried out in a polybag using a manual tumbling method for uniform distribution.

8. Compression:

The final blend was compressed into tablets using a tablet compression machine equipped with appropriate tooling. Uniform tablet weight, hardness, and thickness were monitored during compression to ensure quality compliance.

Formulation chart of mango ginger tablet						
Ingredients	Uses	B1	B2	B3	B4	B5
Mango ginger	Drug	500mg	500mg	500mg	500 mg	500mg
Starch	Diluent	65mg	60mg	55mg	55 mg	50mg
poly vinyl pyrrolidone (pvk 30)	Binder	15 mg	20mg	25mg	-	-
Talc	Glidant	5mg	5mg	5mg	5mg	5mg
Magnesium stearate	Lubricant	5mg	5mg	5mg	5mg	5mg
Cross povidone	Super disintegrants	10mg	10mg	10mg	10mg	10mg
Hydroxy propyl methyl cellulose (HPMC)	Binder	-	-	-	25mg	30mg
Total weight	600 mg					

Evaluation of tablet

1) Pre-compression test

2) Post-compression test

Pre-compression test

1) Angle of repose [13]:

It is the greatest angle that can exist between a powder pile's surface and the horizontal plane. A powder blend that had been precisely weighed was placed in the funnel. The funnel was raised or lowered until its tip just touched the top of the powder mixture. The powder mixture was permitted to freely flow to the top of the funnel. Using the provided formula, the powder cone's diameter was measured and its angle of repose was computed.

$$\Theta = \tan^{-1} (h/r)$$

2) bulk density [14]:

As defined, loose bulk density was by taking a sufficiently weighed amount of powder in the measuring cylinder. The initial volume occupied by the powder is recorded. It is defined as the ratio of weight of powder in grams to the loose bulk volume (cm³).

$$\text{bulk density (BD)} = \frac{\text{weight of powder}}{\text{bulk volume}}$$

3) tapped density [15]:

it is the ratio of the powder mass to the tapped powder volume. The required amount of the powder blend was placed in a 100 ml graduated cylinder and vibrated for a specific number of taps until the volume of the powder bed reached a minimum tapped density based on the following formula.

$$\text{tapped density} = \frac{\text{Weight of powder}}{\text{tapped volume}}$$

4) Hausner's ratio [16]:

hausner's ratio, which measures how easy it is for powder to flow, is computed using formula.

$$\text{hausner ratio} = \text{tapped density} / \text{bulk density.}$$

5) Carr's index (CI) [16]:

The carr's index of a material can be estimated using bulk and taped density measurements. Carr's index was calculated using:

$$100 \text{ is CI. (\%)} = \frac{\text{tapped density} - \text{bulk density}}{\text{tapped density}} \times 100$$

Relationship between angle of repose, Hausner's ratio, percent compressibility and flow property [17]

Flow characteristics	Angle of repose	Hausner's ratio	Percent compressibility
Excellent	25-30	1.00-1.11	1-10
Good	31-35	1.12-1.18	11-15
Fair	36-40	1.19-1.25	16-20
Passable	41-45	1.26-1.34	21-25
Poor	46-55	1.35-1.45	26-31
Very poor	56-65	1.46-1.59	32-37
Extremely poor	>66	>1.60	>38

Post compression test of tablet [18]**1. Appearance & organoleptic properties**

- **Description:** visual inspection of the tablet's color, shape, size, surface texture, and odor.
- **Importance:** ensures uniformity and absence of physical defects (e.g., cracks, capping, lamination, sticking)

2. Thickness & diameter

- **Test method:** measured using Digital Vernier calliper, micrometers, or an automated tablet tester : should be within $\pm 5\%$ of the standard size.
- **Importance:** ensures proper packaging, coating, and uniformity of tablet.

3. Weight variation test

- Test method: weigh 20 tablets individually and compare their average weight to pharmacopeial limits.

Sr .no	USP	Max % difference allowed	I/BP
1.	130mg > or less	±10%	80mg > or less 250
2.	130mg-324 mg	±7.5%	80mg-250mg
3.	324mg < or	±5%	250mg < or more

Importance: ensures uniformity in dosage and API (active pharmaceutical ingredient) distribution.

4. Hardness (crushing strength) test

- Test method: measured using a hardness tester (monsanto, Pfizer, or digital testers).
- Acceptance criteria: typically, 4-10 kg/cm² (varies with formulation).
- Importance: ensures mechanical strength, proper handling, and packaging without breakage.

5. Friability test (mechanical strength)

friability is the phenomenon where the surface of the tablet is damage or shown a site of damage due to mechanical shock. It is tested by using Roche Friabilator. This is made up of a plastic drum fixed with a machine which rotated at 25 rpm for 100 revolutions (25x4=100). Tablet falls from 6 inches height in each turn within the apparatus.

“Roche Friabilator” specification

Internal diameter -283mm-291mm

Depth -36mm-40mm

Inside radius -75.5mm-85.5mm

Outer diameter of central ring -24.5mm-25.5mm

Procedure

For tablets with a unit weight equal to or less than 650 mg, take a sample of whole tablets corresponding as near as possible to 6.5 g. For tablets with a unit weight

- Acceptance criteria (USP/BP/IP standards):

of more than 650 mg, take a sample of 10 whole tablets.

$$\text{Percentage friability} = \frac{w_1 - w_2}{w_1} \times 100$$

W1 = weight of tablets before testing.

W2 = weight of tablets after testing.

Limits: according to B.P/I.P = percentage of friability should be not more than 0.8% - 1.0% according to U.S.P = percentage of friability should be not more than 4%.

6. Disintegration test

Equipment: USP disintegration tester

Test method:

Place 6 tablets in the disintegration apparatus containing water at $37 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$.

Check if the tablets completely disintegrate within the specified time.

Acceptance criteria:

Uncoated tablets: ≤ 15 minutes

Film-coated tablets: ≤ 30 minutes

Enteric-coated tablets: should not disintegrate in acid (1-hour test in HCl) but must disintegrate in buffer (ph 6.8).

Importance: ensures proper breakdown in the digestive system for ape release.

7. Dissolution test (drug release)

Equipment: USP dissolution apparatus (type I – basket, type ii – paddle)

Test method:

Place tablets in a dissolution medium at $37 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$.

Run the test for a specific time (e.g., 30–60 minutes).

Withdraw samples at intervals and measure drug release using a UV spectrophotometer or HPLC.

Acceptance criteria:

Immediate-release tablets: $\geq 75\%$ drug release in 45 minutes.

Sustained-release tablets: as per formulation-specific criteria.

Importance: ensures tablets release the API at the correct rate for therapeutic effect.

8. Drug content

Ten tablets were weighed and powdered and 500mg equivalent weight of mango ginger was accurately weighed and transferred into a 100 ml volumetric flask. It was dissolved and made up the volume with phosphate buffer pH 6.8. Subsequently the solution in volumetric flask was filtered and suitable dilutions were made and analyzed at 268nm using UV visible spectrophotometer. The drug content of each sample was estimated from standard curve of mango ginger using phosphate buffer pH 6.8.

Acceptance criteria: 90–110% of the labelled claim.

Importance: ensures each tablet contains the correct amount of API.

RESULT & DISCUSSION

Phytochemical analysis of mango ginger

The phytochemical screening of the extract revealed the presence and absence of various Phytoconstituents, as summarized in table.

Sr no	Phytoconstituents	Result
1	Terpenoides	+
2	Diterpene	+
3	Alkaloids	+
4	Flavonoids	+
5	Saponins	-
6	Glycosides	-
7	Phenols	+
8	Carbohydrate	-

Determination of calibration curve

1. Spectroscopy study of the mango ginger

Determination of maximum wavelength (max): the UV spectrophotometer with 10mm quartz cuvettes use for determination of maximum wavelength. UV spectrum of mango ginger standard solution will record in the wavelength range of 200-800nm to determine detector wavelength of maximum absorbance (max) using distilled water as blank respectively. It exhibits maxima at 268 nm as shown figure

Determination of standard calibration curve

The UV spectrum of mango ginger in distilled water was found to display absorption maxima at 268 nm. The absorption maxima were found to correspond well with that reported in the literature. The standard calibration curve of mango ginger shows linearity with the R² value of 0.990 at 268nm wavelength which is given in figure 8.2. The slope of the standard curve was used to determine the drug content in most of the in vitro samples generated during the studies. The absorbance of different concentration is given in table 8.2.

Stock solution taken (ml)	Distilled water(ml)	Concentration (Ppm)	Absorbance
0	10	0	0
0.2	9.8	2	0.137667
0.4	9.6	4	0.244333
0.6	9.4	6	0.344
0.8	9.2	8	0.414333
1	9	10	0.487333
1.2	8.8	12	0.540667
1.4	8.6	14	0.612333
1.6	8.4	16	0.688333
1.8	8.2	18	0.779333
2	8	20	0.915667

Linearity graph of standard mango ginger drug

Determination of melting point

Melting point determined by using melting point determination apparatus, melting point of mango ginger was found to be 195°C.

Compatibility studies by FTIR

The FTIR spectral analysis of *curcuma amada* reveals key functional groups that strongly support the presence of labdane-type diterpene dialdehyde, which are associated with anti-tuberculosis (anti-TB) activity. A sharp absorption peak at 1720 cm^{-1} corresponds to $\text{C}=\text{O}$ stretching vibrations, characteristic of Aldehyde groups, a hallmark of the labdane dialdehyde structure. Additional peaks at

$2831\text{--}2974\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (C-H stretching of methyl/methylene), $1514\text{--}1660\text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($\text{C}=\text{C}$ stretching of alkenes/aromatic systems), and $3271\text{--}3500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (broad O-H stretching) further confirm the presence of a Terpinoides backbone with hydroxyl, alkene, and alkyl functionalities.

FTIR interpretations of mango ginger

Wavenumber (cm^{-1})	Functional group	Type of vibration	Interpretation
667	C-H out-of-plane bending	Alkenes/aromatics	Suggests olefinic structure ($\text{C}=\text{C-H}$ bending), supporting the unsaturation in Terpinoides
763–814	C-H out-of-plane bending	Aromatics or isolated alkenes	Confirms presence of isolated double bonds or substituted rings
925–995	C-O or $=\text{C-H}$ bending	Vinyl groups/carbohydrates	Supports alkenic hydrogen bending – consistent with diterpene backbone
1151–1236	C-O-C stretching	Ethers/esters	Supports glycosidic or ester linkages found in some labdane derivatives
1317–1427	O-H bending / C-H deformation	Alcoholic or phenolic groups	Suggests presence of hydroxyl groups (may affect solubility and activity)
1514–1660	$\text{C}=\text{C}$ stretching	Aromatic or alkene vibrations	Indicates presence of conjugated systems (common in diterpene)
1720	$\text{C}=\text{O}$ stretching	Aldehyde or ketone	Key indicator of dialdehyde group in labdane diterpenes (anti-tab core)
2831–2974	C-H stretching	Methyl and methylene groups	Strongly supports presence of aliphatic hydrocarbon chains in diterpene skeleton
3271–3500	Broad O-H / N-H stretching	Hydrogen bonding groups	May indicate alcohol groups or secondary amines; relevant to bioactivity
3670–3969	Sharp/free O-H stretching	Free hydroxyls	May relate to unbound hydroxyl groups in diterpene structures

The FTIR spectral analysis of pure mango ginger and its mixtures with excipients reveals the consistent presence of key functional groups characteristic of the labdane diterpene structure. Notably, the persistent c–h stretching vibrations (2972, 2937 cm^{-1}), Aldehyde c–h stretching (2831 cm^{-1}), and conjugated c=o stretching (1658, 1643 cm^{-1}) confirm the chemical integrity of the active compound even in the presence

of excipients. The presence of skeletal ring vibrations and out-of-plane bending modes further supports the retention of the substituted cyclic structure. Overall, the spectral data indicate no significant chemical interaction or degradation of mango ginger upon formulation with excipients, suggesting compatibility and chemical stability in the final preparation.

FTIR interpretations of mango ginger and Excipients

Wavenumber (cm^{-1})	Functional group	Type of vibration	Interpretation
3880 – 3676	O–h(alcohol, phenol)	Stretching (broad)	Presence of hydroxyl group, possibly due to phenols or alcohols in Terpinoides
2972, 2937	C–h (alkane)	Stretching	Methyl/methylene groups typical of hydrocarbons
2831 – 2831	C–h (Aldehyde)	Fermi resonance/stretch	Aldehyde c–h stretch possibly indicating dialdehyde (e.g., labdane diterpene)
2364 – 2357	Co ₂ / impurities	Asymmetric stretching	Often due to atmospheric co ₂ or minor impurities
1658 – 1633	C=c / c=o (conjugated)	Stretching	Possibly α,β -unsaturated carbonyl (common in diterpenes)
1565 – 1514	N–h bending / aromatic c=c	Bending/stretching	Suggests aromatic amines or aromatic rings
1421 – 1232	C–h / c–n / c–o	Bending/stretching	May be due to esters or amines from plant or Excipient
1151 – 1076	C–o–c (ether), c–o (alc)	Stretching	Suggests alcohols or ethers
1018 – 925	C–o (primary alcohol)	Stretching	Carbohydrate-like structure (from plant/excipients)
758, 667	Aromatic c–h out-of-plane	Bending	Indicates aromatic substitute

Pre –compression test

Batch	Bulk density (g/ml)	Tapped density (g/ml)	Carr's index (%)	Hausner's ratio	Angle of repose (°)
B1	0.476	0.50	4.80	1.050	28.10
B2	0.472	0.493	4.25	1.04	27.70
B3	0.470	0.490	4.08	1.04	27.30
B4	0.490	0.521	5.95	1.06	28.45
B5	0.510	0.549	7.10	1.08	29.37

Post compression test of tablet

Appearance & organoleptic properties

Physical evaluation	B1	B2	B3	B4	B5
Shape	Cylindrical oval				
Colour	Yellow	Light yellow to yellow brown	Yellowish brown	Yellow to mustard brown	Yellow to mustard brown
Texture	Coarse	Smooth surface	Smooth surface	Coarse & granular	coarse & granular
Odour	Characteristic mango ginger aroma				

Batch	Hardness (kg/cm ²)	Thickness (mm)	Weight variation(g)	Friability (%)	Drug content (mg)	Disintegration time (min)	In vitro percentage drug release (%)
B1	7	4.23	516±25.8	0.055	71%	5min	63.22±59
B2	7.5	4.67	599.7±29.98	0.462	95.7%	5 min	95.74±0.009
B3	8	4.70	599.9±29.99	0.153	98.1%	5min	99.22±0.08
B4	4	4.69	599.8±29.99	1.85	92.8%	20 sec	-
B5	4.2	4.67	599.6±29.98	1.54	91.9%	35 sec	-

In-vitro drug release:

To assess the drug release behaviour of formulations b1,b2 and b3 an in-vitro drug release research was carried out during a 60-minute period. Table and

figure show the cumulative percentage of medication release from each formulation at various time intervals.

Result of in-vitro drug release

Time (mins)	In-vitro drug release		
	B1	B2	B3
0	0	0	0
10	0.547±0.011	10.48±0.01	9.66±0.007
20	11.98±0.27	24.17±0.02	26.17±0.01
30	23.69±0.46	40.01±0.01	43.24±0.08
40	35.65±0.54	57.30±0.01	61.15±0.08
50	48.53±0.46	75.78±0.009	79.72±0.08
60	63.22±59	95.74±0.009	99.22±0.08

The in vitro dissolution study demonstrated significant differences in the release profiles of the three batches. Batch b1 showed a moderate drug release of 63.22 ± 5.9 at 60 minutes, whereas batches b2 and b3 exhibited enhanced dissolution, releasing 95.74 ± 0.009 and 99.22 ± 0.08 of the drug, respectively, within the same time frame. Among all, batch b3 showed the most efficient drug release, indicating superior formulation performance and optimal dissolution characteristics. These results suggest that b3 is the most promising batch for achieving rapid and complete drug release in vitro.

SUMMARY & CONCLUSION

Summary

The aim of this research was to develop and evaluate mango ginger tablets by investigating the effect of different binders and their concentrations on tablet properties. Five batches (b1 to b5) were formulated using a constant drug amount (500 mg of mango ginger) with varying levels of diluents (starch), binder (pvp k30 or HPMC), and other excipients like Croscopovidone, talc, and magnesium stearate.

Formulation details:

Batches b1, b2, and b3 used polyvinyl Pyrrolidone (pvp k30) as binder at 15 mg, 20 mg, and 25 mg respectively. Batches b4 and b5 used Hydroxy propyl methyl cellulose (HPMC) at 25 mg and 30 mg respectively. Croscopovidone (10 mg) was used as a super-disintegrants in all batches. Total tablet weight was maintained at 600 mg for all batches.

Pre-compression evaluation (powder blend flow properties):

- Bulk density ranged from 0.470 to 0.510 g/ml and tapped density ranged from 0.490 to 0.549 g/ml.
- Carr's index values ranged between 4.08% and 7.10%, which indicates excellent flow ability (values <15% are desirable).
- Hausner's ratio ranged from 1.04 to 1.08, further supporting good flow characteristics.
- Angle of repose values were below 30° for all batches, indicating good flow.

These results demonstrate that all powder blends had acceptable flow properties, ensuring uniform die filling during compression.

Post-compression evaluation (tablet characteristics):

- The appearance and organoleptic properties of five batches (b1–b5) of mango ginger tablets were evaluated based on shape, colour, texture, and odour. All batches showed a consistent cylindrical oval shape, indicating uniform die and punch operation. Colour varied slightly among batches, with b2 and b3 showing more uniform yellowish to brown shades, suggesting better blending and compression. Texture analysis revealed that B2 and B3 had smooth surfaces, while B1, B4, and B5 te to poor flow or

compression issues. All batches retained the characteristic aroma of mango ginger, indicating preservation of volatile constituents during tablet processing.

- Hardness: batches with pvp k30 binder (b1 to b3) showed higher hardness (7–8 kg/cm²) compared to HPMC batches (b4, b5) which had lower hardness (4–4.2 kg/cm²).
- Weight variation: batches b2 to b5 met the pharmacopoeial limits for weight variation ($\sim 600 \text{ mg} \pm 5\%$), but b1 showed significant deviation ($516 \pm 25.8 \text{ mg}$), indicating poor uniformity.
- Friability: b1 to b3 batches exhibited low friability values ($<0.5\%$), indicating good mechanical strength, whereas b4 and b5 had higher friability ($>1.5\%$), indicating tablets are more prone to chipping or breaking.
- Drug content: b1 had poor drug content (71%), which is below acceptable limits, while b2, b3, b4, and b5 had drug content above 90%, demonstrating good drug uniformity.
- Disintegration time: all batches with pvp k30 binder (b1 to b3) disintegrated within 5 minutes, which is ideal for immediate-release tablets. Batches with HPMC (b4, b5) disintegrated much faster (20-35 seconds), batches b4 and b5 (with HPMC binder) showed significantly lower hardness (4–4.2 kg/cm²) and higher friability (1.54%–1.85%), suggesting fragile tablets prone to mechanical damage.
- In vitro drug release: only batches b1, b2, and b3 were evaluated due to the poor mechanical properties of b4 and b5. Batches b2 and b3 showed excellent drug release profiles, with b3 achieving 99.22% release at 60 minutes, indicating optimal bioavailability. B1 showed poor release (63.22%).

CONCLUSION

The study demonstrated that:

Binder type and concentration critically influence tablet properties: increasing pvp k30 concentration from 15 mg (B1) to 25 mg (B3) improved tablet hardness, drug content uniformity, and drug release. HPMC at 25-30 mg (B4, B5) resulted in tablets with fast disintegration but poor mechanical strength (high friability), making them unsuitable for handling and packaging.

- Batch B3 was identified as the best formulation: from the organoleptic and appearance evaluation, batch B3 was identified as the most acceptable formulate on due to its smooth surface, uniform colour, and retention of mango ginger aroma. These attributes reflect good formulation design and process control. Hence, B3 is suitable for further in vitro and in vivo evaluations, and the organoleptic profile supports its potential acceptability and compliance for patient use. It exhibited ideal flow, good mechanical strength (hardness 8 kg/cm²), and passed all physical tests including friability and weight variation. It showed the highest drug content (98.1%) and excellent in vitro drug release (99.22% within 60 minutes).the 5-minute disintegration time meets immediate release criteria.
- Batch B1 failed due to poor weight uniformity, low drug content, and insufficient drug release: likely caused by low binder concentration (15 mg pvp k30), resulting in weak tablet formation and inconsistent drug distribution.
- Batches B4 and B5, while disintegrating rapidly, failed friability tests indicating weak tablet.

The study concludes that batch B3, containing 25 mg pvp k30 as binder, 10 mg Crospovidone As Superdisintegrants and 55 mg starch as diluent, is the optimal mango ginger tablet formulation. It balances mechanical strength, rapid disintegration, and excellent drug release, making it suitable for scale-up and further development.

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